

Women Education: Its Meaning and Importance in India

Dr.S.Saravanakumar

Assistant Professor of Political Science

Gobi Arts & Science College, Gobichettipalayam

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Saravanakumar, S.

“Women Education:

Its Meaning and

Importance in India.”

Shanlax Internatioal

Journal of Arts, Science

and Humanities,

vol. 6, no. S1, 2019,

pp. 272–76.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2586451)

[zenodo.2586451](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2586451)

Introduction

Education is considered as the only tool for the sustainable development of every society. Women are also a big part of the society. In India, women education has become a major milestone for their empowerment as educated women can also play a very important role inside as well as outside at the development of country. Women’s education is an educational initiative that has been embraced by our country. Today our nation is empowering women more and more to access quality education because women and girls’ education is essential not only to promoting gender equality but also to addressing the full spectrum of 21st century challenges. Since its Independence, India has been developing women education by implementing new policies, programs, schemes and recommendations in favor of them for having access quality education. Women have also been improving their education but it is not sufficient for the needs of the nation and not as equal as men developing. But, in spite of having such new policies and programs, women of our country remain far behind from men in the field of education. This paper is conducted by details study, observation and survey following a variety of recently published articles, researches, data related to education, Government reports, women’s rights and gender inequality to finding out a number of common challenges, issues, problems and barriers which are preventing women in accessing quality education..

Importance of Women Education

Women education refers to every form of education that aims at improving the knowledge, and skill of women and girls. It includes general education at schools and colleges, vocational and technical education, professional education, health education, etc. Women education encompasses both literary and non-literary education. Educated women are capable of bringing socio-economic changes. The constitution of almost all democratic countries, including India, guarantees equal rights to both men and women.

Women comprise approximately half of the population in the world. But the hegemonic masculine ideology made them bear a lot as they were denied equivalent opportunities in different parts of the

world. The augment of feminist ideas has, however, led to the marvelous development of women's condition in the society through out the world in recent times. Access to education has been one of the most urgent and important demands of these women's rights movements. Women education in India has also been a chief preoccupation of both the government and social or civil society as educated women can play a very important role in the development of the country.

In the present era, the Indian society has established a number of institutions for the educational development of women and girls. These educational institutions aim for immense help and are concerned with the development of women. In the modern society, women in India have come a long way. Indian women is at par with men in all kinds of tasks like reaching the moon, conquering Mount Everest, and participating in all fields. All this is possible just because of education and the profound impact it has had on women.

Women's Education in Ancient India

In ancient India, women and girls received less education than men. This was due to the set social norms. Interestingly, in the Vedic period women had access to education, but gradually they had lost this right. Women education in ancient India prevailed during the early Vedic period. In addition to that Indian scriptures Rig Veda and Upanishads mention about several women sages and seers. Women enjoyed equivalent position and rights in the early Vedic era. However, after 500 B.C, the position of women started to decline. The Islamic invasion played a vital role in restricting freedom and rights of the women. A radical change attended and there was a terrific constraint for women education in India.

Women's Education in Medieval India

Women education in medieval India further weakened and declined with the introduction of Purdah system . Different customs and conventions of diverse religions like Hinduism, Islam, and Christianity further deteriorated and depreciated the state of women in the country. A range of socio religious movements contributed to the development of women literacy in the country. Many leaders took several initiatives to make education available to the women of India. The ordered form of women education in India was incorporated in the early centuries of the Christian era.

Women's Education in Colonial India

The position of the women education in India revived with the invasion of the British in the country and with the advent of Bhakti movement. The colonial period also introduced the institutional form of imparting learning. Women education in Colonial India witnessed an essential expansion. Various movements were launched to make women of the country literate. Further more, this progress journeyed through the years and influenced the modern Indian education system.

Women's Education in Modern India

The idea of women empowerment was introduced at the International Women Conference at Nairobi in 1985. Education is milestone of women empowerment because it enables them to responds to the challenges, to confront their traditional role and change their life. So that we can't ignore the significance of education in reference to women empowerment India is poised to becoming superpower, a developed country by 2020. This can became reality only when the women of this nation became empowerment. India presently account for the largest number of illiterates in the world. Literacy rate in India have risen stridently from 18.3% in 1951 to 64.8% in 2001 in which enrolment of women in education have also risen sharply 7% to 54.16%.

Despite the significance of women education unfortunately only 39% of women are literate among 64% of the man. Within the framework of a democratic polity, our laws, development policies, plan and programmes that have focused at women's progression in different spheres. From the fifth five year plan (1974 - 78) onwards has been a marked shift in the approach to women's issues from welfare to development. In recent years, the empowerment of women has been accepted as the vital concern in determining the status of women in the Indian society. The National Commission of Women was set up by an Act of Parliament in 1990 to safeguard the right and legal entitlements of women. The 73rd and 74th Amendments (1993) to the Constitution of India have provided for reservation of seats in the local bodies of Panchayat and Municipalities for women, laying a sturdy basis for their contribution in decision making at the local level.

Moreover, the Central Government of India has recently launched the Saakshar Bharat Mission for Female Literacy, which aims to reduce female illiteracy and spread education and awareness even in the most remote and rural parts of the nation.

The main problems facing their education are:

1. Development of immorality;
2. Suitable Curriculum for the education of girls;
3. Lack of social consciousness among women;
4. Scarcity of lady teachers;
5. Lack of proper physical facilities;
6. Unwillingness of lady teachers to serve in rural areas;
7. Financial difficulties;
8. Problem of transport;
9. Problem of wastage and stagnation;
10. Problem of co-education;
11. Lack of enthusiasm and interest of the officials in charge of education

The education of girls and women is an integral part of national development. Steps that are being taken to improve and expand their education will not recede to the background due to lack of finance. It must be remembered that there is still a big gap to be filled between the education of the boys and girls, further; mother is the pivot of family life in India. Our way of life depends on her. It is essential; therefore, that at least the programmes for girls and women that have already been included in the current plan are not disturbed.

The lack of coordination that existed between the home, the school and the life outside had to be remedied; and a close integration must be secured between the process of education and the social and economic life of the country. Everyone should be trained to make an adequate living and to fill effectively her appropriate place in life.

The facilities for education should be adjusted as accurately as possible to the actual needs and opportunities which arise. Any wastage of training should not be tolerated in a country so poor as India. The methods of education had to be so designed that the inherent appeal and the value of education would win for it the loyalty of the pupils and support of the parents.

The awakening among Indian women has been really considerable during recent years. Despite all obstacles and many difficulties women education is advancing steadily. They are making their influence felt in international affairs. Inside the country there is a demand for equal rights. Indeed, it is quite obvious that women's education must catch up with men's education as rapidly as possible and that great gap between the two must be bridged.

Apart from being a wife and mother, a women must play a positive role in the country's planning and progress and she must develop her own talent. She then to achieve her two rolls of wife and

mother, and a worker to her country, and she can only do this with the mutual co-operation of educational set up of her country and herself Our girls have all the potential qualities, mental, physical, but these will have to be nourished and cherished until they grow into the full and glorious womanhood.

Our late Prime Minister Pandit Nehru said, “the most reliable indicator of a country’s character is the status and social position of women more than nothing else. He said, “I am quite convinced that in India today progress can be measured by the progress of women’s of India”. Dr. Radha krishanan quoting Manu believed “Where women are honoured there the Gods are pleased, where they are not honoured all work becomes fruitless”. Women as human beings have as much right as men have and the honour they expect in society depends on the degree of their education.

Before drawing conclusion it may be mentioned that the task of the school authorities in India is to prepare the girls for the triple role she will have to play in adult life. First, as the founder and fashioner of a happy home, secondly to be able to earn her livelihood independently an honourably if circumstances demand her to do so and thirdly to discharge her duties as a responsible and enlightened citizen.

The Indian Education Commission 1964-66, rightly emphasized, “For full development of our human resources, the improvement of homes and for moulding the character of children during the most impressionable years of their infancy, the education of girls is of greater importance than that of boys”. However, the change in the attitude of the public towards women’s education would go a long way in improving the situation.

Conclusion

Women play an imperative role in making a nation progressive and guide it towards development. They are essential possessions of a lively humanity required for national improvement, so if we have to see a bright future of women in our country, giving education to them must be a pre-occupation Empowerment means moving from a weak position to execute a power. The education of women is the most powerful tool to change the position of society. Education also brings a reduction in inequalities and functions as a means of improving their status within the family. To encourage the education of women at all levels and for dilution of gender bias in providing knowledge and education, established schools, colleges and universities even exclusively for women in the state. The education develops the idea of participation in government, panchayats, public matters etc for elimination of gender discrimination.

References

1. MC.Reddeppa Reddy, P.Adinarayana Reddy (2013) “Education and Women Empowerment”, The Associated Publishers, ISBN 81-8429-055-1, Ambala City (India), 2013.
2. Dr.AaradhanaSalpekar (2013) “Women’s Education”, JnanadaPrakashan (P&D), ISBN-978-81-7139-572-9, New Delhi, 2013.
3. ShyamKartik Mishra, Pradeep Kumar Pandey (2013) “Women’s Share” In family resources in India”, Manglam Publishers and Distributors, ISBN 978-81-89972-89-9, Delhi, 2013.
4. Arpita Sharma (2013) “Women Empowerment and Twelfth Five –Year Plan Approach towards Twelfth Plan”, Discovery Publication house Pvt. Ltd, ISBN 978-93-5056-351-9, New Delhi, 2013.
5. Dr. AaradhanaSalpekar (2013) “Women and Law”, JnanandaPrakashan (P&D), New ISBN 978-81-7139-573-6, Delhi, 2013.
6. Dr. Tanuja Trivedi and JnanadaPrakashan (PanD) (2013) “Status of Women” ISBN: 978-81-7139-562-0, New Delhi, 2013.

7. S.K.PanneerSelvam, (2013) “Women Empowerment and Education”, Discovery Publishing House Pvt.ltd, New Delhi, 2013.
8. Rabindra Kumar (2013) “Dalit Exclusion and Subordination”, ISBN: 978-81-316-0560-8, Rawat Publications, New Delhi (2013).
9. Dr.Tanuja Trivedi, JananadaPrakashan (PanD) (2013) “Women Equality and Development”, ISBN: 978-81-7139-574-3, New Delhi, 2013.
10. Dr.Rameshwari Pandya, Ms.Darshana Patel, Ms.Janki Patel, Ms. ToshaShahu, (2013) “Women Empowerment through Income Generation”, Swastic Publications, ISBN: 978-93-81991-42-8, New Delhi, 2013.

Web Sources

1. <https://www.importantindia.com/17061/women-education-its-meaning-and-importance/>
2. <https://www.prod.facebook.com/mutantedu/posts>
3. <https://phdessay.com/women-education-in-india-2/>
4. <https://www.coursehero.com/file/ppdhc8n/Womens-education-in-modern-India-The-idea-of-women-empowerment-was-introduced/>
5. <https://www.bartleby.com/essay/National-Policy-for-the-Empowerment-of-Women-FK-JNYZEKRZYA>
6. <http://www.yourarticlelibrary.com/essay/problems-and-issues-of-women-education-in-india/44862>
7. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1081705.pdf>